

MIDDLE-MANAGER MEETINGS CHARACTERISTICS AND MANAGERS' INNOVATIVE WORK OUTPUT: THE MODERATING ROLE OF EMPLOYEES' WELL-BEING

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

Meetings at work are the organization's most time-consuming and costly activity (Allen et al., 2018; Mroz et al., 2018). Many meetings are ineffective and cause opportunity costs (Bürkland et al., 2019), causing low morale for employees (Geimer et al., 2015). Employees often attend an average of six hours per week for meetings, which can be up to 23 hours per week with managers (Mroz et al., 2018; Rogelberg et al., 2007). However, meetings also share knowledge and information (Ditillo, 2012; Mroz et al., 2018). They are also believed to be a management control and resource allocation and positively promote innovation project development (Bürkland et al., 2019).

Besides, innovation is widely considered significant to organizations' effectiveness and development (Janssen, 2000; Oldham & Cummings, 1996) because it helps increase productivity and create more added value and competitive advantage for businesses (Damanpour, 1991). Focusing on knowledgeseeing might provide employees with many sources for generating novel ideas (Dahlander et al., 2016). Thus, potentially enhancing their innovative work output (IWO) (Badir et al., 2020). Therefore, this study suspects that meetings may positively impact the IWO. However, because more than half of meetings in the contemporary are believed ineffective (Lehmann-Willenbrock et al., 2017), and most meetings are proven to have a positive relationship with low employees' well-being (Luong & Rogelberg, 2005; Rogelberg et al., 2006). Therefore, we subject that some characteristics of meetings may have a negative relationship with IWO.

Moreover, employees' well-being (EWB) has been one of the essential factors in helping the sustainable development of organizations and society (Abid et al.,

2020) because it is related to employees' attitudes, behavior, and performance. Literature review on EWB showed that most studies believed that the negative form of EWB (i.e., emotional exhaustion) is negatively related to positive outcomes of employees (i.e., IWO).

Therefore, this study has two research questions:

1. What is the relationship between middle managers' meeting characteristics (meeting loads, meeting subjects, meeting management) and their IWO at the workplace?
2. What is the moderating role of EWB (e.g., emotional exhaustion) in the relationship between meeting characteristics and IWO?

To answer the research questions, we establish the objectives of this thesis. Accordingly, we aim to:

1. Examine the relationship between middle managers' meeting characteristics (meeting loads, meeting subjects, meeting management) and their IWO at the workplace.
2. Examine the moderating role of EWB (e.g., emotional exhaustion) on the relationship between meeting characteristics (meeting loads, meeting subjects, meeting management) and IWO at the workplace.

RESEARCH MODEL AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Figure 1. The conceptual model of the middle managers' meetings characteristics and managers' innovation performance

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORKS

Attention-based theory (ABT) and job demand-resource (JD-R) theory will be applied to explain the relationships of this research. ABT is an essential theory lens to observe how people obtain and interpret information from middle managers' meetings (Ocasio, 1997). Based on ABT, characteristics such as meeting load, subject relevance, and management effectiveness might attract managers' attention to the information generated from the meetings (Ocasio, 2011). Therefore, attention in this context can be understood as the "noticing, encoding, interpreting, and focusing of time and effort" (Ocasio, 1997) of managers on the correct and helpful information. In other words, the constrain of people's attention to a few available information and how people interpret this information play as a filter to seek and select the useful one for managers (Junge et al., 2023).

JD-R theory (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017) explains how the balance of job demand and job resources affects employee performance (i.e., IWO) through the two processes, weakening and reinforcing (Roczniewska et al., 2022). (1) Weakening: job demand factors such as workload, emotional requirements, and conflicts take away employees' physical and mental energy to respond to them. As a result, these workloads will cause job insecurity, requiring adaption and task allocation capacity (Janssen, 2000) and reducing employee innovation and creativity (BosNehles et al., 2017). (2) Reinforcing: job resources, such as support for autonomy, relationships, learning, and development, help employees feel satisfied with basic needs and see selfdeveloped (Roczniewska et al., 2022). Thus, it supports employees in achieving their goals at work (Bakker et al., 2008; Demerouti et al., 2001; Xanthopoulou et al., 2007) and promotes creativity and innovation (Bos-Nehles et al., 2017).

HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

Meeting frequency is the average number of meetings that employees attend per week (Rogelberg et al. (2006). Meetings can provide information (Ditillo, 2012) positively related to IWO (Badir et al., 2020). Therefore, based on JD-R theory, meetings can be believed to be innovation resources. However, managers' attention to meetings rather than work time can affect their performance (i.e., IWO) because of limited time and energy (Dahlander et al., 2016). So, according to ABT, it might harm managers' selective information for innovation (Junge et al., 2023). Thus, we establish hypothesis 1 as follows:

Hypotheses 1: Middle managers' meeting frequency has an inverted U-shape effect on managers' IWO.

Meeting length is the number of time that employees spend in each meeting (Rogelberg et al., 2006). Long meetings might cause workload (Rogelberg et al., 2006) and reduce managers' attention (time, energy) to developing new ideas.

Thus, it will likely impair managers' innovation ability (Dahlander et al., 2016). Therefore, under JD-R and ABT theoretical lens, we establish hypothesis 2 as follows:

Hypothesis 2: High middle managers' meeting length is associated with lower managers' IWO.

Meeting subjects' relevance is defined for this study. The meeting is relevant to someone if it is directly or indirectly connected to their work or duties. Meeting subjects relevant to the individual's tasks and role may help exchange information and increase innovation (Bürkland et al., 2019). Relevant meetings might play as resources positively related to IWO (Bos-Nehles et al., 2017; Dediu et al., 2018; Huhtala & Parzefall, 2007). Besides, the meetings that are relevant to managers might attract their focus on noticing, selecting and processing information generated from the meetings to useful applications in their work innovation (Ocasio, 1997). Therefore, under JD-R and ABT theoretical lens, we establish hypothesis 3 as follows:

Hypothesis 3: Middle managers' meeting subject relevance is positively related to managers' IWO.

Meeting management mentions the quality of experiences about the effectiveness of the meeting (Rogelberg et al., 2006). Effective meeting management will become an instrument for knowledge integration (Ditillo, 2012), resource control and promoting employee innovation (Bürkland et al., 2019). Effective meeting management might create helpful information, so it is a resource and positively relates to IWO (Bos-Nehles et al., 2017; Dediu et al., 2018; Huhtala & Parzefall, 2007). Furthermore, effective management drives managers to focus on selecting and processing these information to create innovative ideas (Junge et al., 2023). Therefore, under JD-R and ABT theoretical lens, we establish hypothesis 4 as follows:

Hypothesis 4: Middle managers' meeting management effectiveness is positively related to managers' IWO.

Emotional exhaustion (EE) is the most obvious demonstration of burnout and is a symptom of stress resulting from physical and mental exhaustion (Maslach et al., 2001). Because EE is a kind of energy demand (Warr, 1987), this demand might reduce employees' performance & innovation (Amabile et al., 2002; Bakker et al., 2004). Besides, employees' EE can potentially reduce extra-role efforts (Moliner et al., 2008). Therefore, we establish the subsequent hypotheses as follows:

Hypothesis 5a: Managers' EE strengthens meeting frequency's negative impact on IWO (right-side of U-shape).

Hypothesis 5b: Managers' EE strengthens meeting length's negative impact on IWO.

Hypothesis 5c: Employee EE weakens meeting subject relevance's positive impact on IWO.

Hypothesis 5d: Employee EE weaken meeting management effectiveness's positive impact on IWO.

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

Many research related to meetings at work, EWB and IWO use quantitative methods to test the relationship between them and others' constructs (Badir et al., 2020; Darvishmotevali & Ali, 2020; Luong & Rogelberg, 2005; Rogelberg et al., 2006; Van Minh et al., 2017). Therefore, we also selected quantitative research to examine the relationship between middle managers' meeting characteristics (meeting load, meeting subjects, meeting management) and their IWO under moderating EWB.

We plan to choose middle managers as the target of our survey. Individuals who hold managerial positions between the foreman and divisional executive officer levels are known as middle managers (Larsen, 1993). They follow orders from higher-level executives and have the autonomy to make decisions related to critical strategic projects (Wilden et al., 2022). In this study, managers who perform managerial tasks instead of supervising hourly workers would be included in our survey because they attend many meetings (Mroz et al., 2018), they can contribute to selecting innovative projects (Wilden et al., 2022), and they have the power to implement innovative ideas (Badir et al., 2020).

Our research will be conducted in three steps. The first step is questionnaire design, where the expected outcome is the draft questionnaires. Based on the literature review of the topic, we found the construct of meeting and IWO. Then, we establish the research objects and build the conceptual model. Next, we search the related theories and previous studies to make a platform for hypothesis and measurement development. The second step is the pilot survey to confirm the reliability of measurement, focused on testing the reliability of the scale specifically designed for this study. Then we will build a final questionnaire. The third step is the primary survey to collect the data and conduct analysis to test the measurement and structural model (see Figure 2)

Figure 2. The process design

MEASUREMENTS

Regarding the measurement of meeting frequency and meeting load, we plan to ask people the average number of meetings they attended per week or the average duration of each meeting with their superiors, managers, clients, or subordinates. Besides, we will use a Likert scale with 7 points to measure other construct variables (See Appendix).

FINDINGS

We are in the process of Advancement To Candidate (ATC); our expected findings now are that the meeting characteristics of middle managers may impact their IWO. Besides, we also expect that EWB will play the moderating role of this relationship.

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

First, our research on the meeting characteristics is a new approach—previous research about the meetings considered meeting loads and effectiveness as separate. Second, the relationship between meeting characteristics and IWO is also a

new consideration. Third, the moderating role of the negative form of EWB is an addition to the research about the moderating role of EWB (Wright et al., 2007).

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

Research limitations/implication: We plan to conduct the study in Vietnam to apply the research result to a context similar to Vietnam (an emerging country). Besides, we plan to conduct samples in various industries, so our data might lack consistency, and our explanation might be complex because of our limited knowledge. However, our research expects to fill the gap in the relationship between meetings' characteristics and IWO, especially in the managers under the moderating role of EWB.

Practical implications: We hope this research will highlight the role of middle managers' meeting characteristics, EWB, and IWO in the organizations. Then, the practical leaders will have some decisions to improve the meetings at work to enhance the positive performance of their units and company.

Social implications: By highlighting the role of EWB, this research potentially contribute to the improvement of sustainable employment of organization and contribute to the work-life balance and healthier for the employees as a member of family and society.

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APPENDIX

MEETING SUBJECTS

1. The content of the meetings is related to your current works
2. The purpose of the meetings is to help you achieve the work's goals
3. You must attend those meetings to get your work done
4. Most of the meetings you participated in are really needed for you

MEETING MANAGEMENT - ADAPTED FROM ROGELBERG ET AL. (2006)

1. Achieving your own work goals
2. Achieving colleagues' work goals
3. Achieving your department/section/unit's goals
4. Providing you with an opportunity to acquire useful information
5. Providing you with an opportunity to meet, socialize, or network with people
6. Promoting commitment to what was said and done in the meeting

IWO - Badir et al. (2020)

In your job, how often do you?

1. Make suggestions to improve current products or services
2. Produce ideas to improve work practices
3. Actively contribute to the development of new products or services
4. Optimize the organization of work

Emotional exhaustion - Bedford et al. (2022), adapted from Maslach & Jackson (1981)

1. I feel emotionally drained from my work
2. I feel used up at the end of the workday
3. I dread getting up in the morning and having to face another day on the job
4. I feel burned out from my work
5. I feel I am working too hard on my job